
IMPACT OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT ON EMPLOYEES' PRODUCTIVITY IN THE 21ST CENTURY: A CONCEPTUAL APPROACH.

BY

Abdullahi Ibrahim Wushishi
DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION AND MANAGEMENT
NIGER STATE POLYTECHNIC, ZUNGERU
BIDA CAMPUS
GSM: +2348032936545

Mohammed Nura Adamu
DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION AND MANAGEMENT,
NIGER STATE POLYTECHNIC, ZUNGERU,
BIDA CAMPUS.
E- mail: nuramaijamaa@gmail.com
GSM: +2348066027919

Abubakar Umar Faruk
DEPARTMENT OF MARKETING
NIGER STATE POLYTECHNIC, ZUNGERU,
BIDA CAMPUS.
GSM: +2347035783062

Abstract

Employees are vital organizational asset that must be proactively or reactively empowered through training and development to bridge the knowledge and skills gap created by the current dynamic working environment. Training and development are a veritable tool used in providing employees with the requisite knowledge and skills to effectively and efficiently undertake job task.

This project aimed at assessing the impact of training and development on employees' productivity, the identification of the relationship therein and to suggest how business organizations can enhance the productivity of its workforce to meet challenges of the 21st century.

The conceptual literature review approach was adopted in this paper which involves critically reviewing articles, periodicals, books published in English language between the years 2000 to 2023 with the view of synthesizing information on 'training and development on employees' productivity' based on the analysis from existing studies.

The paper reveals that employees who are trained are likely to be more skilful, competent, and more proficient in performing their jobs than the employees' that are not trained.

Training and development programs are aimed at upgrading both employee and organizational productivity. It is a process of continuous learning which provides conducive environment for employees to gain various knowledge, skills (personal, technical and professional) and keeping them on the right track towards the achievement of organizational mission, vision and goal.

It was concluded that training and development has a positive impact on employee productivity and organizations should lay emphasis and embark on effective training and development of its employees to increase their productivity and gain competitive edge over competitors. Implication for future research may include moderating variables such as age, team work, life style and level of education.

Keywords: Human Capital, Training, Development, Employee, Productivity.

INTRODUCTION

The 21st-century business and work environment is marked by increasing instability and uncertainty (Masa'deh et al., 2015; Orozco et al., 2015), driven by factors such as technological progress, intense competition, greater globalization (Shannak et al., 2010; Masa'deh, 2013), and the rising demand for skilled and competent employees to boost organizational productivity, all of which pose significant challenges to organizational operations (Masa'deh et al., 2016; Obeidat et al., 2016). As a result, businesses are increasingly focused on utilizing their resources to attract, retain, and sustain a talented workforce (Singh and Mohanty, 2012). Organizations are investing heavily in employee training to prepare them for success in this dynamic environment, aiming to build competitive advantage, improve productivity, and support organizational success and ongoing development (Al-Azmi et al., 2012; Alshurideh & Alkurdi, 2012; Almajali et al., 2016; Altamony et al., 2016).

Training and development are essential tools for enhancing human capital by improving knowledge, skills, capabilities, and productivity, as well as strengthening the organizational workforce and securing a competitive advantage in today's work environment (Barsh et al., 2008). The workforce of an organization is a valuable intellectual asset (Kaur, 2016) that requires ongoing training through re-skilling, up-skilling, or both, enabling organizations to leverage these capabilities for competitive advantage and success in the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Hajir et al., 2015; Obeidat et al., 2016; WEF, 2018). Effective training and development programs offer significant benefits to organizations, such as building individual and organizational capabilities, supporting organizational change (Valle et al., 2000), improving talent retention (Jones & Wright, 1992), and ultimately fostering competitive advantage (Youndt et al., 1996; McKinsey, 2006). Training and development are crucial at all employee levels, as skills tend to deteriorate over time and must be continuously updated (Nishtha & Amit, 2010).

Therefore, for organizations to survive in this current dynamic business environment and attain competitive edge, employee training and development must be considered as an invaluable tool for building employee competences, enhancing productivity, gaining competitive advantage and sustainability.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The primary objective of this paper is to evaluate the effect of training and development on employee productivity and explore the relationship between them. An additional objective is to investigate how training and development in the workplace affect employees' knowledge and skills.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This paper seeks to address the following questions:

- Does training & development have positive impact on employees' productivity?
- What are the objectives of training and development in the workplace, whether they are achieved and to what extent?
- How does training and development enhance employees' technical know-how (competencies) and professional skills in the workplace?

LITERATURE REVIEW

EMPLOYEE TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

Several authors have defined training and development in many ways and these two concepts have distinguishing attributes as identified by Noe (2008), which includes; goal, participation, work experience, and focus. In the concept of 'training', goal is to acquire skills for a present job, participation being mandatory once initiated, low work experience, and focuses on current job while in the concept of 'development', goal is to acquire skills for future jobs, voluntary participation, moderate or high work experience, and focuses on future jobs (Noe, 2008).

It can be deduced from literature that training highly focuses on capability enhancement of the workforce through learning and is directly linked to productivity and performance. Training is defined as a way of building employee confidence in the workplace towards enhancing better performance (McClelland, 2002). According to Bramley (2003) training is conceived as a planned process of facilitating employee learning of the job for them to be effective in performing certain or all aspects of their work. In the same vein, Pilbeam & Corbridge (2002) view training as a process of identifying training needs, planning, designing, delivering and evaluating training outcomes. Training is also conceived as a systematic process of knowledge, skills and attitudes enhancement towards satisfactory employee job performance (Obisi, 2011). Similarly, Chiaburu & Takleab (2005) opines that training is a planned activity which is aimed at strengthening employee performance on the job. Furthermore, training is viewed as a process which involves series of activities set up by organizations to bridge and transform an existing gap in employees' knowledge, attitude and skills towards achieving better performance and attainment of organizational objectives (Abomeh & Peace, 2015). Additionally, Kaur (2016) asserts that training is an endless activity aimed at providing the employees with the requisite knowledge and skills to effectively perform their jobs, meeting current job requirement as well as preparing them for the imminent changes occurring in the modern workplace and their jobs.

Development on the other hand is an activity that is self-directed, requiring self-motivation and exploring various means of personal and career development (Noe, 2008). According to Armstrong (2009), Khawaja & Nadeem (2013) development aims at the acquisition of modern knowledge and skills for the progress of a future job requirements. Employee development

involves the act of building the capacity and capability of individual employee towards meeting standard level of performance in the future (Jelena, 2007). Similarly, Obisi (2011) asserts that development is broad in scope and emphasise on personal growth of employees on a long-term basis to address a job requirement in the future. Thus, it can be observed that development is also geared towards enhancing employee performance, personal employee growth and often related to address a future job requirement. However, training and development is considered as one in this project for the sake of simplicity, ease and clarity.

Training and Development is defined as a systematic process of developing knowledge related to work and employee's expertise towards the improvement of jobs performance (Swanson & Holton, 2001). In addition, Akdere (2003) conceived that training and development are practices that reflect parameters used for advancing the level of self-awareness & skills of employees towards effective job performance.

Hence, training and development is a logical and more organised means through which knowledge, skills and attitude of employees with respect to their jobs are improved. Both concepts are related to productivity while training focus on current jobs, development focuses on likely future jobs. Essentially, the sole objective of training and development is to enhance both employee and organizational productivity as well as the attainment of the organizational goals. Training and Development further depicts formal organizational effort in enhancing productivity through numerous educational programs and techniques.

IMPORTANCE OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

Contemporary organizations make significant investments in employee training and development with the primary goal of enhancing productivity, profitability, gaining a competitive advantage, ensuring sustainable growth (Kaur, 2016), and fostering organizational development (Nelson et al., 2012). This is only feasible through a well-properly trained and highly developed organizational workforce who directly or indirectly contributes towards attaining organizational efficiency, productivity, growth and reputation in the current work and business environment (Akbar & Matto, 2010). Moreover, trained employees are conceived as company intellectual assets that are highly correlated to success and are acquainted with the present trends in the modern workplace and market environment (Wheelen & Hunger, 2012) which tends to either reduce or avert operational losses likely to be incurred because of ignorance (poor knowledge) or inadequate employee skills (Zhou et al, 2011). Furthermore, having a skilled base employee, growth enhancement and guaranteed long-term business success is another objective aimed to be achieved by several companies (Salas et al, 2012).

However, there are various specific Training and Development objectives depending on the type of organization and their training needs assessment for specific jobs which often emanates from the analysis of job requirement (examining job description), performance appraisal (measuring employee performance against standard performance), human resource survey (identifying areas of deficiencies) and organizational analysis (Infande, 2015). In view of the above, the major objectives of Training and Development to various organizations can be geared towards achieving some of the followings; Increased organizational productivity, building competitive advantage, profitability, cost effectiveness, organizational growth & development, reputation, survival and sustainability. All of which are only achievable through a well-trained organizational workforce.

Training and Development are significantly important as they are the catalyst for progress and growth for emerging and existing businesses and economies, and they are used as tools for responding to the dynamic trends of globalization, uncertainty, growing clients/customer expectation and technological exploitation (Hung, 2010) in this 4th Industrial Revolution working environment of today (WEF, 2018). Training & development is very important to both employees and organizations in numerous ways.

Firstly, it improves employee morale, satisfaction, job security, productivity which in turn leads to an increase in organizational productivity (Onyango & Wanyoike, 2014).

Secondly, employee self- efficacy is developed through training and development (Tahir et al, 2014) thereby resulting to the removal of weak traditional work practices and replacing them with modern practices in the workplace (Wajidi & Tabassum, 2016) and in turn leads to organizational effectiveness and efficiency.

Thirdly, it helps in decreasing employee anxiety and frustration which may emanates from their inability to perform their jobs/work to the desired level and may also influence their decision to leave the organization, resulting to higher rate of employee turnover (Chen et al., 2005). It bridges the gap between the required necessary skill for the job and that which is possessed by the employee, the lower the gap the higher employee job satisfaction and vice-versa. Trained employees display a high level of satisfaction on their work and are capable of satisfying customers/clients satisfactorily (Rowden & Conine, 2005).

Fourthly, it helps in improving employee morale (through increasing their confidence & motivations), reduces cost of production (through avoiding waste and reducing operational risks), reduces absenteeism and the rate of labour turnover, enhanced staff quality and achievement of organizational goal (Cole, 2002).

Lastly, it is an important tool for managing organizational change through employee participation (involving them actively) in the change process, educating and equipping them with the necessary skills required for new, changing and complex situations (Cole, 2002) modifying the work related behaviour of employees and encouraging them to actively partake towards achieving organizational success and yielding greater return (Mamoria, 1995) as well as improving its profitability base (Tahir et al, 2014).

Therefore, it can be deduced that the imperative of training and development to both employees and organization is enormous and cannot be underestimated. A major objective of business organization is profitability, growth and sustainability which depends on revenue (Singh & Mohanty, 2012) and the revenue cycle is controlled by knowledge, creativity and innovation of which all emanates from organizational workforce (employees) (Kaur, 2016). Thus, training these work force for development leads to productivity which in turn generates this revenue. Training and development do not only improve productivity but inspire and motivate employees towards performing their task making it inevitable to all organizations in the modern business and work environment.

EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY

The concept of productivity refers to the ability to complete work-related tasks according to a set standard, focusing on accuracy, speed, cost, and completeness (Sultana, Irum, Ahmed, & Mehmood, 2012). Several scholars have offered definitions of employee productivity. For example, Kaur (2016) emphasizes that employee productivity is tied to an employee's ability to finish tasks, which is closely linked to work output, timeliness, and quality. Ferreira & Du Plessis (2009) define it as the time spent on a task based on job responsibilities, leading to the

desired outcome. Rohan & Madhumita (2012) describe it as an economic measure of output relative to input per unit, which can be assessed individually (for an employee) or collectively (for the economy) (Singh & Mohanty, 2012). Additionally, Mathis & Jackson (2008) suggest that employee productivity can be evaluated based on both the quality and quantity of work completed, considering the cost of the resources used. In conclusion, improving employee productivity is essential for enhancing overall organizational productivity and efficiency.

Employee productivity is one of the critical challenges that organizations recently face towards work force management (Hanaysha, 2016). This is because employee productivity is achieved through the utilization of various organizational inputs/ resources (money, machines, methods, materials) and it is influenced by several behavioural and environmental factors (Bhat, 2013). Major behavioural factors influencing employee productivity are employee training, employee empowerment and team work (Bhat, 2013). Environmental factors influencing employee productivity consist of enabling and conducive working environment (Hameed & Amjad, 2009), adequate office equipment, lightening, temperature, noise free environment, befitting physical office layout (Vasudevan, 2014), a well-developed sound culture of safety at work (Newstrom, 2002), healthy management-subordinate relationship and employees and industrial peace (Nilsen, 2002), befitting physical office layout, and the existence of a reasonable balance of power, control and authority in making decisions (Brown, 2008). Employee productivity is considered as one of the major determinants for organizational success (Najeeb, 2013) which emanates from competent management (Vrat et al, 2009) and through effective training and development programs (Nelson et al, 2012; Bhat, 2013). For this reason, organizations must strive in identifying significant factors that are responsible in influencing employee productivity as well as developing suitable training and development programs that will facilitate and leads towards organizational productivity.

Training and development is regarded as a very important tool that is effective and essential towards achieving organizational mission, objectives and goals which in turn result to increased productivity (Colombo & Stanca, 2008; Sepulveda, 2010;). In the same vein, Glaveli & Karassavidou (2011) asserts that adequate provision of appropriate training to employees often leads to reduction in cost of production, increased innovation and higher productivity. In addition, Rowden (2002) assert that training can be used to improve employee job satisfaction which may also lead to increased productivity. Thus, implying that training can lead to employee satisfaction which in turn will reflect on his level of productiveness.

However, Kawara (2014) opined that associating reward to productivity and performance through various incentive schemes either financial (cash bonuses) or non-financial (recognition, awards, vacation,) is a common approach that leads to employee satisfaction and can influence employee productivity. This indicates that a trained employee can still be less productive if there is absence of certain environmental factors such as good corporate culture, power & politics within the organization, group dynamics, job design and an effective appraisal system. For this reason, these environmental factors must be considered in the quest for achieving the effectiveness of training as well as ensuring its positive impact on employee productivity (Wright & Geroy, 2001).

From the foregoing, it can be observed that employee productivity can be influenced by numerous factors either behavioural or environmental as disclosed by several scholars ranging from enhanced working environment, management-subordinate relationship, reward systems, safety and equipment. This imply that training alone without considering other factors may not be enough for the attainment of employee productivity. The productivity of

an employee depends not only on training but the level of employee freedom (allowing him/her to put into practice whatever learnt during the training and development exercise, taking part in strategic decision-making process and freely decides on the jobs they are responsible for) coupled with the availability of certain environmental factors such as conducive working environment. However, effective training can be considered as a major factor for enhanced employee productivity because employees can be satisfied when they have the feeling of being competent and capable of handling their jobs effectively and efficiently. Therefore, employees who undergo effective training programs often display higher level of job satisfaction and tends to be more productive.

METHODOLOGY

Methodology includes critical conceptual reviews (synthesis) of related literature on the impact of training and development on the employees' productivity. It is based on the analysis and insights drawn from the existing literature of numerous studies on training and employees' productivity (articles, periodicals, books). The resources (articles) used in reviewing the literature are sourced using search engines and data bases such as Web of Science, Science Direct, Google scholar, and EBSCO to source for related articles. The entire search was limited to peer reviewed articles published in English language within the period of 2000 to 2023, which were reviewed critically and further analyzed. The rationale behind the period restriction was to get broad and latest information from current related articles and latest findings on the topic. Key words utilized in search for useful and related information includes; Human Capital, Training, Development, Employee, and Productivity.

FINDINGS AND IMPLICATIONS

The reviewed literature indicates that employees are the most active, unique, and valuable resources within an organization, and they cannot be easily replicated by competitors. Therefore, it is crucial to manage them effectively and efficiently to improve organizational productivity and performance. Training and development have been shown to positively influence employee productivity, aligning with findings from previous studies (Riyaz, 2004; Dearden et al., 2006; Konings & Vanormelingen, 2010; Verma & Goyal, 2011; Sultana et al., 2012; Bhat, 2013; Kaur, 2016). The goals of training vary according to organizational needs, employee assessments, technical analysis, personal development plans, and the aim to boost productivity.

In the 21st century, organizations implement training programs to enhance productivity, profitability, competitiveness, organizational development, and long-term sustainability. Training and development are also key to improving employee morale, self-efficacy, reducing turnover, bridging skill gaps, managing change, and increasing job satisfaction, all of which contribute to both individual and organizational productivity (Bhat, 2013; Cole, 2002; Rowden & Conine, 2005). These results are consistent with findings from Nelson et al. (2012) and Kaur (2016), who found that training is strongly linked to improved employee morale, job satisfaction, reduced attrition, and enhanced organizational productivity.

Employee productivity, which directly impacts organizational performance, depends on effective training and development. However, training alone is not enough to ensure productivity; it must be complemented by other factors like a reward system, proper equipment, a conducive environment, and workplace safety (Wright & Gerov, 2001; Nilsen, 2002; Brown, 2008; Kawara, 2014). Training helps employees improve their knowledge, skills, attitudes, and job competence, preparing them for future challenges and enabling them to adapt to the evolving business environment, which ultimately leads to job satisfaction and

enhanced productivity (Kaur, 2016). Furthermore, trained and skilled employees tend to perform their tasks more effectively and are more productive compared to untrained, unskilled workers (Kaur, 2016). A significant discovery from the literature is that training and development are critical tools that drive learning, knowledge, skill, behavior, and competencies, directly influencing employee productivity. These efforts are essential for achieving an organization's mission and vision (Imran & Tanveer, 2015).

IMPLICATIONS

The above findings have the following significant implications for policy makers (organizations, government), future research, theory and practice:

- The work environment of the 21st century is more likely to be of tremendous advantage to organizations that learn fast through training and development and can quickly adapt to the dynamics of the environment than their competitors.
- Trained employees are more likely to experience greater job satisfaction and happiness, which positively impacts their commitment and productivity. In contrast, employees who lack training may become frustrated and dissatisfied, leading to inefficiency, reduced confidence, and lower productivity.
- The findings reveal that organizations interested in achieving high level of productivity and profitability must have an effective and efficient workforce management that lay emphasis on imparting additional knowledge, skills, competencies and modern work practices that can be gained through training and development.
- The findings highlight that organizations that invest in employee training and development are more likely to be appreciated by their workforce. This investment increases the chances of fostering higher employee commitment, morale, and productivity, which is likely to positively impact overall employee performance.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper is basically aimed at assessing the impact of training and development on employees' productivity with a view to examine the relationship between them. Based on the findings of the project, it was concluded that training and development has positive impact on employee productivity and that training and development programs significantly influence employee productivity. Therefore, to achieve the benefits of training and development, organizations should conduct manpower survey to identify the causes of less productiveness, where and how to address the problem, what type of training is required and for who in order to avoid unnecessary expenses and achieve desired training outcome. It is also recommended that business organizations should lay emphasis on training and development of their workforce in order to meet up with the challenges, dynamic trends and market competition in this current era of the Forth Industrial Revolution.

The main limitation of this paper is that it is a conceptual review, focusing primarily on the direct relationship between training and development and employee productivity. Future research could benefit from examining additional moderating factors such as age, education level, gender, and behavioral aspects like teamwork and empowerment. Moreover, further empirical or case study research is needed to gain a comprehensive understanding of how

training and development affect employee productivity and its implications in the 21st century.

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